

HIROAKI OOÏ SPIELT »EINE KLEINIGKEIT INS ALBUM DER FRAU KLEE« VON STEFAN WOLPE (NOV. 2019, TOKYO, WELTPREMIERE)

HIROAKI OOÏ

Hiroaki OOÏ, piano
Native of Kyoto, Hiroaki Ooi received Swiss and Japanese governmental scholarships to study at Hochschule der Künste Bern, where he earned his soloist diploma for piano and concert diploma for harpsichord, working with Bruno Canino and Dirk Börner. He has appeared as soloist on such festivals as La Biennale di Venezia, Musica Viva, Hannover Biennale, the Avignon Festival, the Pan Music Festival (Korea), and performed worldwide with orchestras including Symphonieorchester des Bayerischen Rundfunks, the Ensemble Intercontemporain (Paris), the Deutsches Kammerorchester (Berlin),

Asko Ensemble (Amsterdam), the NHK Symphony Orchestra (Tokyo), the New Japan Philharmonic (Tokyo), the Tokyo Metropolitan Symphony Orchestra, among others.

After the recommendation by the composer himself, with Orchestre philharmonique du Luxembourg, Ooi has recorded Iannis Xenakis' two piano concertos, Synaphai and Erikthton; the former was internationally acclaimed, winning the prestigious Choc des Chocs award, and the latter was the world premiere recording, thirty years since the date of composition.

Official Blog: <https://ooipiano.exblog.jp>

<https://youtu.be/ROBFsHLJuQI>